

The First Public Data from the Gemini High-Resolution Optical Spectrograph

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In the next few years, the International Gemini Observatory, a program of NSF's NOIRLab, is pursuing an ambitious plan for new instrumentation. That plan includes the [Gemini Infrared Multi-Object Spectrograph \(GIRMOS\)](#), the [IGRINS-2 high-resolution near-infrared spectrograph](#), the [SCORPIO optical and near-infrared imager](#), and the upgraded [Gemini Planet Imager 2.0](#). The first of these new instruments — and the first facility instrument that Gemini has commissioned in more than a decade — is the [Gemini High-Resolution Optical Spectrograph \(GHOST\)](#), a new workhorse high-resolution spectrograph that will be available to the community in shared-risk mode in Semester 2023B. GHOST is a fiber-fed, echelle spectrograph with coverage from 363 to 950 nm; it provides two-target spectroscopy at resolutions of greater than 50,000 and single-target spectroscopy at resolutions of more than 75,000.

Over the last few months, GHOST has finished its commissioning work, and the team is now preparing for the first call for proposals. The final step in this process was the end-to-end [system verification \(SV\)](#) conducted in mid-May, in which proposals were selected to go through the full process of proposal submission, observation preparation, and data reduction. Targets were chosen by the instrument science team. This group was selected by the Gemini Directorate, in consultation with the Science and Technology Advisory Committee (which advises the Gemini Board on scientific and instrumentation priorities for Gemini), and the GHOST instrument team. The goals of the SV were to test the full set of GHOST software, documentation, and operational procedures in advance of offering the instrument to the community; to demonstrate to the community the science possible with GHOST; and to provide public, reduced data

Figure 1: Example data from a 1.5-hour GHOST SV observation of 2MASSJ1424, an extremely metal-poor star with enhancements in r-process elements. The panels highlight atomic and molecular absorption features used for the determination of atmospheric parameters (T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$) and chemical abundances. These data will allow for a more complete chemical inventory of this star's atmosphere and a chemo-dynamical analysis that can further constrain its progenitor. *Credit: NOIRLab/AURA/NSF/V. Placco*

Figure 2: An example spectral comparison for the White Dwarf WD 1145+017 from GHOST and the High Resolution Echelle Spectrometer (the long-wavelength configuration; HIRESr) on Keck I. WD 1145+017 is the first white dwarf discovered to show transits from a disintegrating asteroid [2]. Its atmosphere is heavily polluted from accretion of the circumstellar material and GHOST SV data will be used to constrain the evolution of that material over time. *Credit: NOIRLab/AURA/NSF/S. Xu*

that showcase the capabilities of GHOST and in turn helps users to prepare for GHOST’s first open call for proposals.

The science encompassed by GHOST’s initial targets includes the following:

- 1 **Observations of Galactic metal-poor stars:** Chemical abundances of stars in the Milky Way will be used to constrain the progenitors of extremely metal-poor stars, understand star formation at the lowest metallicities, and study the accretion history of the Milky Way disk and the origins of substructures in the Milky Way halo (Figure 1).
- 2 **Transmission spectroscopy of hot exoplanet atmospheres:** GHOST spectroscopy of atomic, ionic, and molecular species in the atmospheres of exoplanets transiting their host stars will be used to study the physical and chemical processes at work in those atmospheres.
- 3 **White dwarfs and symbiotic stars:** GHOST observed O IV line profiles in symbiotic star systems to provide insights into their kinematics, geometry, and evolutionary stages. GHOST also observed a white dwarf with a disintegrating, transiting asteroid and will study the evolution of its circumstellar material (Figure 2).
- 4 **Binary star systems:** GHOST observations of single-lined spectroscopic binaries will reveal their hidden companion stars, allowing the team to investigate accretion processes that shed light on massive star formation. GHOST observations of candidate co-natal stars will be used to study the correlation of metallicity with binary star separation.
- 5 **Chemical abundances of ultra-faint dwarf Milky Way satellites:** Chemical abundance patterns of stars in ultra-faint dwarf galaxies (UFDs), some of the oldest and most metal-poor stellar systems in the local Universe, will be used to explore the star formation and chemical enrichment in environments like those of the first galaxies (Figure 3). GHOST also observed early-type stars in the nearby dwarf galaxy Sextans A.
- 6 **Extragalactic compact systems:** GHOST observations will reveal the chemical compositions of ultra-compact dwarfs — massive, compact star clusters — in order to understand their evolutionary histories. GHOST also observed luminous quasars to study absorption from galaxies along the line of sight to probe galaxy evolution and the formation and distribution of metals in the circumgalactic medium.

Simultaneously, a manuscript with the first science results from GHOST from the commissioning data — spectroscopy

Figure 3: Spectroscopy of metal-poor stars from GHOST's first science results (Hayes et al., 2023). GHOST commissioning data clearly show the enhancement in Mg and C abundances for the star GDR3 0928 (red), allowing it to be identified as a carbon-enhanced metal-poor star in the ultra faint dwarf galaxy Ret II. These data demonstrate how GHOST will help to constrain the metal enrichment, star-formation histories, and evolutionary processes of some of the faintest and oldest galaxies in the Universe. *Credit: C. Hayes/NRC Herzberg Astronomy & Astrophysics*

of metal-poor stars in a nearby UFD — has recently been submitted to AAS Journals [1] (Figure 3). The data allowed the GHOST commissioning team to constrain chemical abundances in the galaxy Ret II, in turn placing constraints on the metal enrichment processes of one of the closest UFDs.

In addition to showcasing the potential science from GHOST, the goal of these data is to help the community prepare for 61 hours of shared-risk observations in Semester 2023B. The first GHOST raw data was [made available](#) to the community in June, and the reduced data will be available by the end of August. The call for proposals will be announced in late August, and Gemini is hosting multiple webinars for the community to prepare for the new instrument.

Our hope is that these data will be the starting point for engaging the community in Gemini's new instrumentation. Over the coming years, observatory staff will be streamlining the process from instrument commissioning to system verification to community engagement and accessibility. We're excited to be at the beginning of a new era for Gemini instrumentation and new science frontiers.

References

- [1] Hayes, C. et al. 2023. [arXiv:2306.04804](https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.04804)
- [2] Vanderburg, A. et al. 2015, *Natur*, 526, 546. [doi:10.1038/nature15527](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature15527)